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The Role of Interpersonal Sexual Objectification in Heterosexual Intimate Partner Violence From Perspectives of Perceivers and Targets

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Abstract

Sexual objectification is a subtle manifestation of sexist discrimination and violence against women that involves seeing and treating women as sex objects of male sexual desire. The primary aim of this research was to connect sexual objectification experiences with heterosexual intimate partner violence. This set of studies examined the impact of sexual objectification on intimate partner violence for both the female victim (Study 1) and the male perpetrator (Study 2). Female (Study 1) and male (Study 2) participants were asked to rate the extent they are victims or perpetrators of sexual objectification experiences and intimate partner violence. Moreover, women's self-silencing and men's ascriptions of humanity and empathy (through empathic concern and perspective taking) toward their partner was assessed. The results of the first study (including 154 heterosexual women) showed that general sexual objectification *victimization* indirectly leads to higher psychological and physical violence through the internalization of self-silence schemas. The second study (including 165 heterosexual men) demonstrated a link between general sexual objectification *perpetration* and psychological and physical intimate partner violence. Moreover, the relation between men's perpetration of objectification and intimate partner violence was mediated by ascriptions of humanity and empathic concern toward their female partner (but not through perspective taking toward her). Results of both studies demonstrate the effect of sexual objectification (as target or perpetrator) on global intimate partner violence and explain the different psychological mechanisms through which it takes place depending on the gendered perspective. Theoretical implications and practical considerations for interventions on intimate partner violence are discussed.

Keywords

Dehumanization, domestic violence, empathy, Intimate Partner Violence, offenders, sexual harassment

One third of women are victims of intimate partner violence (IPV), in which they are physically or psychologically harmed by their romantic partner (World Health Organization [WHO], 2012). While physical violence may be prototypical, IPV is also perpetrated using psychological violence (e.g., claiming to own one's partner; Krantz &

Garcia-Moreno, 2005). A plethora of literature has revealed that being a target of IPV adversely affects women's health (e.g., Stark & Flitcraft, 1996). Moreover, a great deal of feminist work has attempted to identify the causes of IPV, primarily focusing on patriarchal power (Namy et al., 2017). The current work takes a nuanced approach, examining the role power plays in IPV experienced by women and perpetrated by men, through examining sexual objectification of women.

While IPV is an all too common occurrence in the lives of women, sexual objectification—seeing and treating a target as an object for the use of the perceiver (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997), is one of the most widespread demonstrations of gender discrimination, in which women are the primary targets (Gervais et al., 2018). For instance, women report experiencing objectification 3.69 times a week (Holland et al., 2017). Unlike IPV that commonly manifests in overt hostility, verbal threats, and physical assault, objectification usually manifests in relatively subtle harassing behaviors, including body evaluations and sexualized commentary that are sometimes even complimentary in nature (Herbozo & Thompson, 2006). This pervasive and complementary nature of objectification leads women to internalize the objectifying gaze (i.e., gazes at their bodies) through a process termed self-objectification (i.e., adopting another's perspective of their body; Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997). A great deal of research has examined intrapersonal consequences of self-objectification (e.g., depression, eating disorders, and anxiety; see Roberts et al., 2018); however, less research has focused on interpersonal consequences of sexual objectification. The current work examines the possibility that a culture of sexual objectification plays an important role in IPV as experienced by women and perpetrated by men.

Scant research focusing on consequences of sexual objectification occurring within interpersonal contexts identifies the importance of understanding objectification as part of a complex continuum (Gervais & Eagan, 2017). In particular, objectifying gazes are considered subtle manifestations of objectification that provide the foundation for extreme manifestations of objectification, including harassment, rape, and sexual violence (e.g., Gervais et al., 2014). Supporting this notion, empirical studies reveal relations between women's reported objectification and sexual violence victimization, including sexual assault and coercion (Franz et al., 2016; Ramsey & Hoyt, 2015). Moreover, links have been found between men's perpetration of objectification and more extreme sexual violence (e.g., Ramsey & Hoyt, 2015; Rudman & Mescher, 2012).

Yet, given these links, the association between interpersonal instances of sexual objectification and violence occurring within intimate relationships has been relatively unexplored. While recent research has begun to reveal the role of objectification within the context of intimate relationships (e.g., Zurbriggen et al., 2011), the links between objectification and sexual violence suggest that objectification must be understood as a component of IPV. The current work examined the role of objectification in predicting IPV for both female targets and male perpetrators, as an essential step in minimizing the occurrence of IPV. Relative to previous links made between self-objectification, other-objectification, and IPV (Jonsson et al., 2018), the current work takes a nuanced approach by examining mechanisms of this relation from the perspective of both the female target and the male perpetrator.

Female Target Perspective: Self-Objectification and IPV Victimization

Women's internalization of sexism that results from objectifying experiences is related to maladaptive coping strategies (Szymanski & Henrichs-Beck, 2014), supporting the idea that women who experience objectification internalize it, ultimately increasing their IPV victimization risk. Self-objectification, understood as the internalization of

someone else's perspective of one's own body (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997), might be considered as a strategy for coping with gender discrimination in which women do not actively cope with the stressful event, but instead internalize such discrimination. Furthermore, sexual objectification increases women's oppressive ideology endorsement (Calogero & Jost, 2011), increasing their acceptance of IPV (Herrero et al., 2017). Importantly, the occurrence of IPV is due exclusively to the perpetrator, but undermining women's coping abilities and increasing women's acceptance of oppression inhibit women's abilities to end an abusive relationship (Carlson, 1997), in which adequate coping strategies are crucial (Taft et al., 2007). Although women have no control over IPV perpetration, there are behaviors that can promote their safety (e.g., generation of effective self-defense strategies and developing a safety plan; Carlson, 1997; Senn et al., 2013). Promoting women's safety in sexual violence (e.g., Enhanced Assess Acknowledge Act [EAAA] program; Senn et al., 2013) has been shown to be effective in preventing rape among college women (Senn et al., 2015).

To our knowledge, there is no research on the relation between objectification and women's IPV coping strategies, but previous links have been made between self-objectification and IPV. For instance, in a survey of college students, Davidson and Gervais (2015) revealed that more experiences of IPV were related to an increased tendency to self-objectify. Jonnson and colleagues (2018) found further evidence supporting this link, showing that female self-objectification is related to psychological, physical, and sexual victimization. While this previous work implies that IPV leads to self-objectification, the correlational nature suggests an alternative implication that "a tendency to internalize objectifying perspectives of women represents a risk for primary IPV victimization" (Jonnson et al., 2018, p. 34). The current work suggests that an additional external occurrence in the lives of women—interpersonal objectification—may act as a precursor to women's experiences of IPV when women internalize objectifying self-perceptions.

Although detrimental consequences associated with objectification suggest women should not adopt objectifying self-perceptions, research suggests women commonly internalize objectification, commonly manifesting in behaviors that make them appear more object-like. In feminist examinations of women's non-confrontational responses to gender discrimination, researchers conclude that socialization processes teach women the significance of maintaining relationships with men, laying the groundwork for acceptance and internalization of discriminatory behaviors (Jordan, 2010). For example, in interactions with men, women *self-silence*, suppressing their feelings and thoughts and censoring themselves to maintain a relationship (Jack, 1991). Self-silencing becomes a common practice for girls during a time when social pressure about beauty standards becomes resolute (Shouse & Nilsson, 2011), suggesting a link between self-silencing and experiencing objectification. In particular, reporting more experiences of sexual objectification is related to more self-silencing (Sáez, Valor-Segura, & Expósito, 2019). Saguy et al. (2010) for instance, analyzed women's time spent talking in an objectifying social interaction and found that men's appearance focus increased women's self-silencing (as indicated by less time spent talking). Self-silencing appears to be one way women avoid conflict and maintain their relationships after experiencing objectification by oppressing their thoughts and feelings.

While self-silencing may be a means in which women attempt to avoid conflicts, conflict avoidance can be problematic in the context of romantic relationships. For instance, conflict avoidance is related to interpersonal problems primarily due to diminished confidence in personal thoughts and fear of losing an intimate partner (Harper & Welsh, 2007). In the context of romantic relationships, self-silencing is

related to rejection sensitivity (Harper et al., 2006), as well as women's perceptions of their husband as demanding (Uebelacker et al., 2003). Moreover, previous research has revealed that self-silencing may be an internalized form of sexism that maintains violent relationships, with self-silencing correlating with intimate and emotional violence (Whiffen et al., 2007; Woods, 1999). Jack and Ali (2010), in particular, showed that female IPV victims engage in more self-silencing relative to women who have left or have never been in relationships in which IPV occurred. Together, these findings suggest that self-silencing acts as a process through which women become disconnected from their feelings and thoughts, increasing the likelihood they may maintain a tumultuous relationship, even when violence is present (Jack, 1991; Woods, 1999).

Male Perceiver Perspective: Perpetration of Sexual Objectification and IPV

Considering that women's victimization is only one perspective within heterosexual relationships, men's involvement in this ongoing process should be considered. Sexual objectification is a common interpersonal experience in the lives of women, most commonly perpetrated by men (Gervais et al., 2018). When men objectify women, women are perceived as sexual things opposed to people (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997; Loughnan et al., 2010). Theoretically, Nussbaum (1995) asserts that treating someone like an object involves instrumentality, denial of autonomy and subjectivity, perceived inertness and fungibility, as well as violability, and ownership. Perceiving women as objects in which violability—how a perceiver “treats the object as lacking in boundary integrity,” — and ownership —how a perceiver sees a woman as an object “owned by another” (Nussbaum, 1995, p. 257)—are acceptable, may lead to more extreme forms of violence. In line with this suggestion, Ramsey and Hoyt (2015) found that men in heterosexual relationships were more likely to sexually pressure and coerce their partners if they objectified them. In a similar vein, Wright and Tokunaga (2016) showed that objectifying perceptions of women are predictive of more positive attitudes toward violence against women, suggesting a strong association between violence against women and the notion that women are objects. Men who view women through an objectifying lens objectify women in their social environment, including their intimate partner, paving the way for IPV (Gervais et al., 2014). Importantly, men who objectify women are more likely to engage in psychological, physical, and sexual violence toward their partners (Jonsson et al., 2018), suggesting that men's perpetration of sexual objectification plays an important role in IPV perpetration. While Jonsson and colleagues (2018) support that male abusers perceive all women through an objectifying lens, the current work expands upon the understanding of this relation by examining potential mechanisms.

One potential mechanism in the relation between men's perpetration of sexual objectification and IPV is diminished ascriptions of humanity. A long history of research has revealed that dehumanization, or not perceiving someone as fully human, lays the foundation for violence (e.g., Bandura et al., 1975). In the case of relations between men and women, increased implicit dehumanization of women increases the likelihood that men will engage in violence toward women (Rudman & Mescher, 2012). Importantly, sexual objectification of women broadly may be associated with IPV toward men's romantic relationship partner because objectification of women increases dehumanized perceptions of women in general (Loughnan et al., 2010; Vaes et al., 2011) and men's romantic partners specifically. For instance, men who focus on women's appearance are more likely to perceive women as lacking humanity (Bernard & Wollast, 2019), with fewer human attributes (e.g., Heflick & Goldenberg, 2009), and less mind attribution (Cikara et al., 2011)—a trait essential for humanity. Perceiving objectified

women as lacking in mind has been shown to have important consequences for female victimization (Loughnan et al., 2013). Failing to ascribe someone with humanity might play an important explanatory role in the relation between perpetrating sexual objectification and IPV, with dehumanization of women laying the groundwork for violence.

Along with increased likelihood for violence, dehumanization of targets is closely related to diminished empathy toward targets (Haslam, 2006). Moreover, a lack of empathy is one factor related to increased aggressive behaviors (for a review, see McPhedran, 2009). Empathy—the response that someone has as result of another’s experiences (Davis, 1983) is lessened in the case of objectified women who are ascribed less humanity (Cogoni et al., 2018), primarily because humanization is a prerequisite of empathy (Awasthi, 2017; Fiske, 2009). Empathy is multifaceted, consisting of perspective taking, fantasies, empathic concern, and personal distress during intense emotional situations (Davis, 1983). Of these components, perspective taking—the capacity to take another’s point of view, and empathic concern—compassionate feelings for others (Davis, 1983), in particular, may play important roles in the relation between perpetrating objectification generally and violence specifically toward an intimate partner (Hanson & Scott, 1995; Varker & Devilly, 2007). Perspective taking (or the lack thereof) has been hypothesized as an important element of sexual objectification among powerful people (Civile & Obhi, 2016) and helps explain why people fail to consider the suffering of objectified females who have been victimized (Loughnan et al., 2013). Similarly, empathic concern plays a role in objectification of women, with lessened empathic concern toward objectified targets being related to an increased willingness to induce pain toward objectified targets relative to non-objectified targets (Loughnan et al., 2010). In addition, perspective taking and empathic concern have been related to IPV. Greater perspective taking constrains interpersonal aggression (Richardson et al., 1994) and less perspective taking promotes sexual coercion within intimate relationships (Covell et al., 2007). Furthermore, a lack of empathic concern predisposes men to engage in sexual aggression and sexual coercion (DeGue et al., 2010). Together, a lack of perspective taking and empathic concern might diminish men’s positive affect toward his partner and increase the proclivity of IPV (Rakovec-Felser, 2014). As a result, empathy displayed through perspective taking and empathic concerns may play important roles among the relation between perpetration of sexual objectification and IPV, with lessened empathy laying the groundwork for objectifying perceptions to lead up to engaging in IPV.

Overview of Studies

In this set of studies, we expand upon previous work by examining the role of objectification within intimate relationships, as it relates to IPV. Given the common role of men as perpetrators and women as victims of sexual objectification (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997; Gervais et al., 2018), the current work used a dual-sided approach examining objectification and IPV as experienced by women (Study 1) and perpetrated by men (Study 2).

Study 1

Study 1 examined whether women’s sexual objectification victimization is related to a greater tendency to engage in self-silencing behaviors, and whether greater self-silencing is related to higher frequency of being victimized by IPV. Specifically, hypotheses for Study 1 are as follows:

Hypothesis 1: Women's experiences of sexual objectification would be positively related to psychological (Hypothesis 1a) and physical (Hypothesis 1b) violence victimization.

Hypothesis 2: Women's frequency of experiencing sexual objectification would be positively related to the tendency of engaging in self-silencing behaviors.

Hypothesis 3: Greater self-silencing would be associated with higher female experiences of physical (Hypothesis 3a) and psychological (Hypothesis 3b) violence in their romantic relationships.

Hypothesis 4: An indirect relationship would emerge between sexual objectification and psychological (Hypothesis 4a) and physical (Hypothesis 4b) violence through self-silencing.

Method

Participants and Procedure

Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained prior to study recruitment. In total, 187 women were recruited to a survey on Amazon's Mechanical Turk (MTurk) titled "Intimate Relationships and Personal Beliefs." MTurk offers a paid participant pool and the survey link was hosted through Qualtrics.com. Following informed consent, participants completed the measures reported here within the context of a larger survey and they were compensated with US\$0.50. Although race and ethnicity demographics were inadvertently not collected, MTurk was used specifically because participants are more diverse in terms of age and race, and thus are more representative than typical American college samples (Buhrmester et al., 2011). Data were excluded from 33 participants who identified as a gender other than female ($n = 8$), a sexual orientation other than heterosexual ($n = 18$), or because they failed to respond to all of the primary measures (scale-level missing data: $n = 7$), leaving a total of 154 women. All included participants correctly answered the attention check question. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 84 ($M = 37.92$, $SD = 12.05$) years, and the majority of participants (135; 87.7%) described themselves as currently in a committed relationship.

Measures

Sexual objectification victimization. To assess sexual objectification experiences, participants completed the Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale (Kozee et al., 2007). This 15-item scale asks women to report the frequency of which they experience body evaluations (e.g., "How often have you been whistled at while walking down a street?") and unwanted explicit sexual advances (e.g., "How often have you been touched or fondled against your will?") using a scale ranging from 1 (*never*) to 5 (*almost always*). Participants' responses were averaged, with higher scores indicating more frequent objectification victimization ($M = 2.21$; $SD = 0.79$; $\alpha = .96$).

Self-silencing. The degree to which participants silence themselves during interactions with a romantic partner was assessed using the Silencing the Self Scale (Jack & Dill, 1992). Participants indicated their agreement with 31 items (e.g., "I don't speak about my feelings in an intimate relationship when I know they are going to cause disagreement.") using a scale ranging from 1 (*totally disagree*) to 5 (*totally agree*). Responses were summed, with higher scores indicating greater self-silencing ($M = 76.92$; $SD = 19.45$). Item-level data were missing for 10 participants and thus the total score was coded as missing to avoid bias ($\alpha = .91$).

Psychological and physical violence victimization. Finally, participants completed the Abusive Behavior Inventory—Partner Form (Sherpard & Campbell, 1992). This 30-item measure assesses the frequency of experiencing violence in the context of an intimate relationship. Specifically, participants reported on the frequency of experiencing psychological (e.g., “Made you do something humiliating or degrading [like begging for forgiveness, having to ask his permission to use the car or do something]; stopped you or tried to stop you from going to work or school”) and physical (e.g., “Slapped, hit, or punched you”) violence in the last 6 months from their current or former partner using a scale from 1 (*never*) to 5 (*very frequently*). Participants’ responses were averaged for the psychological ($M = 1.57$; $SD = 0.74$, $\alpha = .95$) and physical ($M = 1.31$; $SD = 0.69$, $\alpha = .96$) violence subscales.

Results

Bivariate correlations were first estimated for all variables (Table 1). Consistent with hypotheses, more frequent experiences of objectification were significantly correlated with more psychological (Hypothesis 1a) and physical (Hypothesis 1b) IPV victimization. Moreover, more frequent experiences of objectification were correlated with more self-silencing (Hypothesis 2a). In addition, and in support of hypotheses, women’s engagement in self-silencing was significantly correlated with more psychological (Hypothesis 3b) and physical (Hypothesis 3b) violence victimization in their intimate relationships.

Next, we examined whether the frequency of experiencing objectification is indirectly related to women’s experiences of psychological and physical IPV victimization through the effect of self-silencing (Hypothesis 4a and 4b). We tested our proposed mediational model using multivariate path analysis conducted with Mplus 8 software (Muthén & Muthén, 2010). Data were analyzed using a bias-corrected and accelerated bootstrapping approach with 10,000 resamples to estimate the indirect effect and maximize power while

Table 1. Study 1 Correlations Among Variables for Women.

Variables	1	2	3
1. Objectification experiences	—		
2. Self-silencing	.22**	—	
3. Psychological violence victimization	.49***	.53***	—
4. Physical violence victimization	.48***	.45***	.87***

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

minimizing Type I errors. Bootstrapping provides an empirical approximation of sampling distributions of indirect effects to produce 95% confidence intervals (CI) of estimates (Shrout & Bolger, 2002)—when zero is not within the CI, the indirect effect is different from zero. Full information maximum likelihood estimation was used to address missing data for the 10 participants on the self-silencing scale. Multiple indices were used to assess global fit of the model (i.e., comparative fit index [CFI], root mean square error of approximation [RMSEA], and standardized root mean square residual [SRMR]), revealing the model was just identified.

Results of the indirect effect of experiencing objectification on IPV victimization as mediated by self-silencing are reported in Figure 1. In support of Hypotheses 4a and 4b,

women's more frequent experiences of objectification were indirectly linked to more frequent psychological (unstandardized coefficient = .09, $p = .03$, 95% CI = [.01, .17]) and physical IPV victimization (unstandardized coefficient = .07, $p = .04$, 95% CI = [.01, .14]) through the effect of self-silencing. Yet, the direct effect of experiencing objectification on psychological violence (unstandardized coefficients = .37, $p < .001$, 95% CI = [.25, .49]) and physical violence (unstandardized coefficients = .35, $p < .001$, 95% CI = [.21, .49]), remained significant when accounting for the influence of self-silencing suggesting other unmodeled mechanisms may be present.

Supplemental analysis. Because Jonnson and colleagues (2018) suggested an alternative model in which IPV would predict objectification, we also tested a mediational model with IPV victimization as the predictor, objectification victimization as the outcome, and self-silencing as the mediator (see Supplemental Information). The indirect effect was not present in the model with psychological IPV as the predictor (unstandardized coefficient = $-.04$, $p = .55$, 95% CI = [-.16, .07]) or physical IPV as the predictor (unstandardized coefficient = .005, $p = .91$, 95% CI = [-.08, .10]) of experienced objectification, suggesting that objectification victimization lays the groundwork for IPV victimization (and not vice versa).

Figure 1. Empirical model of the indirect effect of objectification victimization on IPV victimization through self-silencing (Study 1). Top values represent the model predicting psychological violence victimization, whereas the bottom values represent the model predicting physical violence victimization. Values represent the unstandardized coefficients and standard errors.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .0001$.

Study 2

Study 2 explored the relation between men's perpetration of objectification and IPV, specifically testing the roles of two traditional psychological processes related to objectification—humanity and empathy. Specifically, hypotheses of Study 2 are as follows:

Hypothesis 1: Men's objectification of women would be related to increased perpetration of psychological (Hypothesis 1a) and physical (Hypothesis 1b) violence.

Hypothesis 2: Men's sexually objectifying perspectives of women generally would be associated with diminished ascriptions of humanity of their partner.

Hypothesis 3: Perceiving their partner as less than human is related to diminished empathic concern (Hypothesis 3a) and a lack of partner perspective taking (Hypothesis 3b).

Hypothesis 4: Lessened empathic concern is related to higher perpetration of psychological (Hypothesis 4a) and physical (Hypothesis 4b) violence; less perspective taking would be linked to greater perpetration of psychological (Hypothesis 4c) and physical (Hypothesis 4d) violence.

Hypothesis 5: Men's perpetration of sexual objectification generally is indirectly linked to perpetration of psychological (Hypothesis 5a) and physical violence (Hypothesis 5b) through a lack of humanity and empathy toward their partner.

Method

Participants and Procedure

Using similar recruitment methods as Study 1, a total of 195 male MTurk workers participated. Data from 30 participants were excluded because participants did not identify as male ($n = 1$), or heterosexual ($n = 11$), failed the attention check ($n = 3$), or because they failed to respond to all of the primary measures ($n = 15$), resulting in a total of 165 participants. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 70 ($M = 35.66$, $SD = 11.94$) years, and the majority of participants (140; 84.8%) described themselves as currently in a committed relationship. The procedure followed is identical to that of Study 1.

Measures

Objectification perpetration. To assess objectification perpetration, participants completed the Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale–Perpetration version (Gervais et al., 2018). This 15-item scale mirrors the female target version (Kozee et al., 2007) by asking men to report the frequency of perpetrating body evaluations (e.g., “How often have you made inappropriate sexual comments about someone’s body?”) and unwanted explicit sexual advances (e.g., “How often have you touched or fondled someone against her or his will?”) using a scale ranging from 1 (*never*) to 5 (*almost always*). Participants’ responses were averaged ($M = 2.02$, $SD = 0.80$), with higher scores indicating more frequent perpetration of objectification ($\alpha = .94$).

Ascriptions of humanity. Men’s humanization of their partner was assessed using a 8-item modified version Bastian [and collaborators](#) (2013) measure of humanity ascriptions. The current study adapted the original instructions to specify the target person as a romantic relationship partner. Specifically, participants rated the extent to which they ascribed human nature (e.g., “I feel like she is open minded, like she can think clearly about things”) and human uniqueness (e.g., “I feel like she is refined and cultured”) traits to their current or former relationship partner using a 1 (*not at all*) to 7 (*very much so*) scale. The average was calculated ($M = 5.23$, $SD = 1.16$, $\alpha = .87$).

Empathic concern and perspective taking. Men’s empathy toward their romantic partner was assessed with an adaptation of the empathic concern and perspective taking subscales of the Interpersonal Reactivity Index (Davis, 1980). The original scale was modified to specify the target as one’s current or former romantic relationship partner. Participants were asked to rate the descriptiveness of 14 items related to empathic concern (e.g., “I often have tender, concerned feeling for her when she is less fortunate than me”) and perspective taking (e.g., “I try to look at her side of a disagreement before I make a decision”) using a 0 (*does not describe me well*) to 4 (*describes me very well*) scale. Responses were averaged for empathic concern ($M = 2.90$, $SD = 0.76$, $\alpha = .80$) and perspective taking ($M = 2.62$, $SD = 0.69$, $\alpha = .76$).

Psychological and physical violence perpetration. Finally, to assess psychological and physical IPV, participants completed the Abusive Behavior Inventory (Shepard & Campbell, 1992). This 30-item measure assesses how frequently participants perpetrate abusive behaviors in the last 6 months from their current or former intimate relationship using a 1 (*never*) to 5 (*very frequently*) scale. Reported frequency of perpetrating psychological (e.g., “put down her family and friends”) and physical (e.g., “slapped, hit, or punched her”) violence in a relationship was averaged with higher scores indicating more frequent perpetration of psychological ($M = 1.66, SD = 0.90, \alpha = .97$) and physical ($M = 1.41, SD = 0.81, \alpha = .97$) IPV.

Results

Bivariate correlations were estimated for all variables (see Table 2). Consistent with hypotheses, men’s more frequent objectification perpetration was positively correlated with perpetration of psychological (Hypothesis 1a) and physical (Hypothesis 1b) IPV. Moreover, men’s more frequent perpetration of objectification was negatively correlated with humanizing their partner (Hypothesis 2), as well as empathy toward their partner. In support of hypotheses, ascriptions of humanity to their partner were positively correlated with empathic concern (Hypothesis 3a) and perspective taking (Hypothesis 3b) toward their partner. Moreover, as expected, diminished empathic concern was correlated with perpetration of psychological (Hypothesis 4a) and physical (Hypothesis 4b) IPV, and similarly diminished perspective taking was correlated with perpetration of psychological (Hypothesis 4c) and physical (Hypothesis 4b) IPV.

To test the indirect effect of perpetrated objectification on perpetrated IPV through the proposed mechanisms, path analyses were conducted using maximum likelihood estimation, and 10,000 bootstrap resamples using Mplus 8 software (Muthén & Muthén, 2010). The indirect path analysis models are depicted in Figure 2. In the model predicting psychological IPV perpetration, when controlling for all variables, less empathic concern, but not perspective taking, was related to psychological IPV perpetration. Similarly, when

Table 2. Study 2. Correlations Among Variables for Men.

	1	2	3	4	5
1. Objectification perpetration	—				
2. Partner’s humanity	-.41***	—			
3. Partner perspective taking	-.28***	.58***	—		
4. Partner empathic concern	-.35***	.67***	.71***	—	
5. Psychological violence	.75***	-.54***	-.37***	-.50***	—
6. Physical violence	.75***	-.44***	-.30***	-.44***	.92***

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

predicting physical IPV perpetration, when controlling for other variables, less empathic concern, but not perspective taking, predicted physical IPV perpetration. Importantly, the serial mediation indirect effect of objectification perpetration predicting psychological IPV perpetration via humanity, empathic concern, and perspective taking (Hypothesis 5) was partially supported. Consistent with hypotheses, the indirect model via humanity and empathic concern toward their partner emerged (unstandardized coefficient = .06, $p = .01$, 95% CI = [.02, .11]). Yet, the serial indirect effect via humanity and perspective taking did not emerge (unstandardized coefficient = -.01, $p = .48$, 95% CI = [-.05, .02]). Likewise, our hypothesis regarding the indirect effect of

perpetrating objectification on perpetrating physical IPV via humanity, empathic concern, and perspective taking (Hypothesis 5) was partially supported. Consistent with hypotheses, the indirect model via humanity and empathic concern toward their partner emerged (unstandardized coefficient = .06, $p = .01$, 95% CI = [.02, .11]); yet, the indirect effect via humanity and perspective taking did not emerge (unstandardized coefficient = $-.02$, $p = .25$, 95% CI = $[-.06, .01]$).

Supplemental analysis. As in Study 1, we also tested a parallel model in which IPV perpetration was the predictor and objectification perpetration was the outcome (see Supplemental Information). The indirect effects were not present through empathic concern (unstandardized coefficient = $-.02$, $p = .29$, 95% CI = $[-.07, .01]$) or perspective taking (unstandardized coefficient = .008, $p = .65$, 95% CI = $[-.03, .04]$) when psychological IPV perpetration was used to predict objectification perpetration, or through empathic concern (unstandardized coefficient = $-.02$, $p = .27$, 95% CI = $[-.07, .01]$) or perspective taking (unstandardized coefficient = .02, $p = .46$, 95% CI = $[-.02, .06]$) when physical IPV perpetration was used to predict objectification perpetration, suggesting that perhaps objectification perpetration contributes to IPV perpetration through humanity and empathic concern rather than IPV perpetration leading to objectification through similar pathways.

Figure 2. Empirical model of indirect effect of men’s perpetration of objectification toward women generally on IPV perpetration through ascriptions of humanity and feelings of empathic concern and perspective taking (Study 2). Top values represent the model predicting psychological violence perpetration, whereas the bottom values represent the model predicting physical violence perpetration. If just one value appears, it refers to both models. Values represent the unstandardized coefficients and standard errors.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .0001$.

Discussion

This work examined the relation between sexual objectification and IPV. Because of power differences within intimate heterosexual relationships, women are frequent targets of objectification and violence, whereas men more likely to be perpetrators (Strelan & Hargreaves, 2005; WHO, 2012). With this consideration in mind, the current work relied on a gendered perspective by examining, first, how women’s experienced sexual objectification indirectly predicts their IPV victimization through self-silencing. Second, the current work revealed how men’s perpetration of sexual objectification

indirectly predicts perpetration of IPV through decreased perceptions of a romantic partner as fully human with emotions.

Study 1 revealed that for women, experiencing more objectification in their daily lives is associated with increased psychological and physical violence victimization. Moreover, experiencing more objectification predicted women's engagement in self-silencing, which predicted more frequent psychological and physical violence victimization. Furthermore, in line with the gender oppressive ideology associated with the objectification phenomenon (Calogero & Jost, 2011), women's self-silencing mediated the relation between experiencing objectification and IPV. Moreover, the current work extends previous literature, revealing that beyond shaping women's behaviors, engagement in self-silencing shapes the way in which others interact with women. While the current work is not the first to suggest a relation between experiencing objectification and IPV (e.g., Davidson & Gervais, 2015; Jonnson et al., 2018), the model tested suggests that increased exposure to sexual objectification increases women's adherence to self-silencing cognitive schemas. These feelings, beliefs and behaviors then mediate the link between objectification and violence victimization. Importantly, perpetrators of IPV are the sole individuals responsible for this occurrence; yet, society teaches women from an early age that women's value is based predominantly on what she can contribute to men's lives, promoting strategies for maintaining romantic relationships (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997; Witte & Sherman, 2002). When women internalize self-silencing schemas as a result of reoccurring interpersonal objectification, these more subtle instances of sexual violence set the groundwork for victimization of more extreme forms of violence. The current work suggests the existence of a patriarchal system that perpetuates violence against women, meaning that IPV is a societal and not individualized problem.

Study 2 revealed that men's perpetration of objectification toward women in general was associated with perpetration of psychological and physical IPV. This finding replicates previous work revealing the relation between men's perpetration of objectification and violence against women (Gervais et al., 2014) specifically with IPV. Moreover, this finding is consistent with previous research suggesting that men who chronically objectify women have problems in interpersonal interactions with women (Sáez, Riemer, Brock, & Gervais, 2019). The current work identified key mechanisms that may illuminate the relation between men's perpetration of objectification and IPV. Objectification of women was associated with lower ascriptions of humanity toward a romantic partner. This relation has been found previously in the literature on the consequences of objectifying women on dehumanization (Loughnan et al., 2010; Vaes et al., 2011); when men perceive women as sexual objects, they ascribe women with fewer human attributes (e.g., self-restraint, depth, and warmth). Importantly, our serial mediation path analysis revealed that ascriptions of humanity were essential in predicting empathy. For men, perceiving their partner as lacking in humanity predicted a lessened capacity to feel empathic concern toward her as well as a lessened ability to assume her perspective. Given previous relations identified between feelings of empathy and IPV (DeGue et al., 2010), the current work examined how empathic concern and perspective taking predicted perpetration of violence. While empathic concern significantly predicted perpetration of psychological and physical violence with less empathic concern related to greater perpetration, perspective taking was correlated with perpetration of psychological or physical violence, but it does not incrementally predict IPV when accounting for the other variables in the model. It suggests that the lack of assuming female partner's perspective is not the variable that explains violence,

rather it is a specific component of empathy—empathic concern, which is associated with perpetration of IPV.

Of note, the current work revealed that the link between men's perpetration of objectification indirectly predicts perpetration of psychological and physical violence through ascriptions of humanity and empathic concern. These findings suggest that men's objectifying perspective of women generally predicts violence perpetrated toward their partner, specifically because objectifying perceptions decrease the likelihood of perceiving their partner as fully human and with emotions. This is in accordance with results from a study conducted by Baldry et al. (2015) demonstrating that perceived humanness of an intimate partner is essential for willingness to help and support her; yet, this finding also suggests that violence perpetrated toward a female relationship partner might be explained by the same mechanism as violence toward an outgroup (Castano & Giner-Sorolla, 2006).

Generally speaking, results revealed that experienced and perpetrated sexual objectification are strongly related to respective experienced and perpetrated IPV. Our research builds upon previous research linking objectification to IPV by exploring mechanisms to illuminate *why* the relation exists. For women, reoccurring experiences of objectification increase ideological adherence to disempowering beliefs, laying the groundwork for increased tolerance of violence (Herrero et al., 2017). For men, perpetration of objectification increased dehumanized perspectives of their partner and lessened concern for her emotions, laying the groundwork for violence against them. In other words, men's objectifying lens toward women predicted difficulties in perceiving and treating a romantic partner as a person deserving of non-violent interactions (Gervais et al., 2018).

Although the current work illuminated novel mechanisms, it is not without limitations. For instance, the current studies focused solely on one side of the phenomenon. While we attempted to achieve a balanced gendered perspective by focusing on women's experiences in Study 1 and men's perpetration in Study 2, this perspective overlooks how these experiences unfold within the relationship of a specific couple. While we found that women's experiences of objectification from men generally and men's perpetration of objectification toward women generally shaped the ways in which they perceived a romantic partner specifically, it is possible that objectification experienced from or directed toward one's partner may more strongly predict experienced and perpetrated violence. Future work should consider examining objectification within a dyadic framework. In the current work, we attempted to examine this model within a diverse sample through the inclusion of MTurk workers. Yet, because race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, and other intersections of identity can impact objectification and IPV, future work should explore these models with attention to the ways in which key demographic characteristics may further shape the relations between objectification and IPV among women and men.

The current models were developed based on empirical literature regarding objectification, dehumanization, and IPV; however, the use of mediational analyses with correlational data presents a limitation. Specifically, because of the cross-sectional nature of the data, caution is needed when attempting to interpret potential causes and the direction of effects. While past research has demonstrated a reverse pathway with IPV predicting more frequent experiences of objectification (Jonsson et al., 2018), a similar tested model in which IPV predicted objectification victimization in Study 1 and perpetration in Study 2 was not supported. Objectification has been suggested to lie along a continuum of sexual violence (Gervais et al., 2014), and our results demonstrate that engagement in more subtle forms of violence through objectification is associated

with more extreme forms of violence through the tested mechanisms. Specifically, objectification predicted IPV due to relations between objectification and dehumanization (e.g., Loughnan et al., 2013; Vaes et al., 2011) and dehumanization and violence (Bandura et al., 1975). Although theory supports the mechanisms examined, the current work is only correlational, and thus causal interpretations should not be made. Future research should examine these phenomena within a laboratory setting or with repeated measurements over time to better assess cause and effect. Finally, the correlational nature of the current work included a reliance on self-report measures which may have biased participants' answers. For example, participants may have distorted ratings of their behaviors due to the sensitive nature of the items of some scales (e.g., objectifying behaviors are perceived as normal by a lot of men and therefore they may have been underreported because they do not perceive objectifying gazes or comments as inappropriate). As a result, we suggest that our measures if anything provide a more conservative test of our hypotheses; yet, we encourage researchers to carry out future studies using implicit measures for evaluating objectifying perception of women and its relation with IPV (i.e., expanding upon Rudman & Mescher, 2012).

Conclusion

Together, the current work demonstrates the importance of considering sexual objectification as a manifestation of gender violence. When women are sexually objectified, cognitive processes are altered within the mind of the perceiver (Bernard et al., 2012; Gervais et al., 2012), hindering attributions of humanity to women. In the past decade, Harvey et al. (2007) promoted efforts to eradicate IPV that "are not grounded in an understanding of risk factors or in social science theory regarding behaviour and social change." With this call to ground interventions in science, our research provides empirical support to the idea that psychological and physical violence toward women starts when men perceive women through an objectifying lens, denying them the ability to consider women as humans with emotions that matter. Together, our findings suggest that intervention programs focused on cognitive training to increase perceptions of women's humanity, like those already in progress focused on improving socio-cognitive domains among IPV perpetrators (Romero-Martínez et al., 2016), might be an effective intervention for IPV.

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Supplemental Material

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